

FMEA 2.0: Machine Learning Applications in Smart Microgrid Risk Assessment

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Abstract—Modern Smart Grids are complex systems incorporating physical components like distributed energy resources and storage, along with cyber components for advanced control, networking, and monitoring. Reliability assessment is a systematic evaluation process used to identify, interpret, and eliminate potential failures and enhance overall reliability of the systems such as Smart Grids where safety is a critical factor. Failure Mode and Effects Analysis (FMEA) is one of the risk analysis tools used for evaluating and prioritizing potential failure modes and improving reliability of systems and processes. Within traditional FMEA, failure modes are ranked using a numerical assessment called the Risk Priority Number (RPN), derived from the multiplication of three factors: severity, occurrence, and detection. While commonly used, the FMEA approach has shortcomings, such as assuming equal importance of factors and not adhering to the ordered weighted rule. For this reason, this study proposes an integrated methodology for risk prioritization and failure mode classification into low, moderate and high-risk faults using Grey Relational Analysis (GRA) together with FMEA and Deep Learning algorithms. The results demonstrate that, especially in complex systems like Smart Microgrids, the proposed method more accurately captures the coupling relationships between failure modes compared to the conventional FMEA method.

Index Terms—FMEA, GRA, Clustering, Smart Grid, RPN, Fault, Risk Assessment, Deep Learning, DEC

I. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, with a rising focus on sustainable energy development, innovative technologies like artificial intelligence, smart sensing and digital twins are transforming the energy sector. Smart Microgrids, an innovative extension of traditional microgrids, offer great benefits such as improved electricity generation, increased energy security, reduced disruptions, and sustainable power supply [1]. The integration of renewable energy sources, electric vehicles, and energy storage systems into microgrids' infrastructure expands its resource capacity and fortifies storage capabilities, creating a more versatile and resilient energy infrastructure [2]. In contrast to regular grids, which are typically governed by the electric companies and limit demand response to large consumers, Smart Grids facilitate bidirectional connectivity and intelligent demand response allowing users of varying scales to actively manage and optimize electricity consumption [3]. Smart Grids also use information and communication technologies to automatically collect and analyze energy data, enhancing efficiency, and

reliability in electricity production and distribution, while providing insights into supplier and consumer behavior [4].

Complex systems like Smart Grids that integrate diverse technologies are susceptible to failures and disruptions. If not proactively addressed, these issues can lead to significant operational challenges, compromising overall system stability. Therefore, it is important to have a comprehensive understanding of the diverse failure modes, their root causes, and consequential effects. For this task, the application of Failure Modes and Effects Analysis (FMEA) can be applied. FMEA is a systematic methodology employed to identify and assess potential failure modes within different industries, evaluate their effects, and prioritize them based on their risk levels, enhancing the overall resilience and dependability of systems [5]. In the context of Smart Microgrids, where timely detection and mitigation of faults are critical, it is crucial to implement enhanced risk assessment and diagnostic tools capable of capturing early fault signatures, enabling proactive measures to maintain system stability and optimize the microgrid's efficiency [6]. To address these challenges, researchers have conducted various risk assessment studies. For example, in their literature review, Hare et al., presented a comprehensive survey on fault diagnostics in smart microgrids, offering valuable insights for engineers developing fault-tolerance and mitigation strategies [7]. Also, Akula and Salehfar analyzed critical failure modes in cyber-physical components within microgrids and evaluated classical FMEA's capability to identify infrastructure weaknesses and enhance reliability [8]. Likewise, Carro et al., introduced a methodology for a comprehensive risk assessment in the construction of a CaL-based Thermal Energy Storage prototypes in a solar thermal plant, highlighting construction and operational risks, control measures, and insights for designing prototypes [9].

While FMEA is a commonly employed method in various industries, both practitioners and academic researchers point out numerous challenges in its effective implementation, such as insufficient historical data, difficulty of understanding complex behaviors in large systems, rapid technological development, etc. [10]. To address these issues, several authors have introduced enhanced risk assessment analyses techniques. For example, Baynal et al. employed an integrated approach, combining Grey Relational Analysis (GRA) with FMEA to en-

hance Risk Priority Number (RPN) and achieved a remarkable improvement in addressing door seal cuts problem in automotive manufacturing [11]. Filz et al. presented a data-driven FMEA methodology using Deep Learning on operational data from the aviation sector and achieved high accuracy in fault prediction, eliminating subjective estimations and enhancing transparency for maintenance planning [12]. Similarly, Peddi et al. introduced a modified FMEA using Deep Neural Networks for an automated and continuous RPN prediction for various stages of the food supply chain, eliminating the need for human intervention in periodic updates [13].

This paper examines the application of novel Machine Learning techniques to enhance the FMEA process, specifically focusing on Smart Microgrids. It proposes an optimized method that combines FMEA and GRA to address the shortcomings of the traditional FMEA approach while effectively prioritizing failures within these intelligent energy systems. A Deep Learning-based algorithm called Deep Embedded Clustering is integrated into the risk assessment framework to classify failure modes with different criticality levels. As a result, the proposed novel ranking algorithm prioritizes mitigation actions based on specific criteria for each failure mode aiming to optimize the reliability and resilience of Smart Microgrids and their digital twins.

II. METHODOLOGY

In this study, we employ a hybridized methodology that combines different Machine Learning algorithms together with FMEA and GRA methods to improve the risk prioritization of failure modes. The methodology is thoroughly described in the following sections.

A. Failure Modes and Effect Analysis (FMEA)

FMEA is a structured and systematic approach used to identify, prioritize, and mitigate potential failures in a system, process, or product, while also assessing their potential impact on performance [14]. It was first developed by the US military in the 1940s as a tool for improving the reliability of military equipment and later gained widespread adoption across diverse industries, including aerospace, automotive, healthcare, food service and manufacturing [15]. The main FMEA process involves a team of experts who collaborate to identify the likelihood of failure modes and their effects aiming to re-design or modify processes to minimize risks. The procedure includes the estimation of occurrence, severity, and detection for each identified failure, whether known or potential [16]. Occurrence represents the likelihood of failure and its cause, detection involves the evaluation process to uncover potential failures in the product, and severity expresses the importance and urgency of potential system default modes. Traditional FMEA assigns risk priorities to failure modes using the RPN, calculated on a 10-point scale by multiplying the severity (S), occurrence (O), and detection (D) of each failure, such that $RPN = S \times O \times D$, where a higher RPN value indicates a higher priority. To evaluate the significance of each identified failure mode, an extended methodology called Failure Mode,

Effects, and Criticality Analysis (FMECA) is employed. This approach builds upon the foundation of Failure Mode and Effects Analysis (FMEA) and includes an additional step to assess the criticality of each identified failure mode, such that $Criticality = S \times O$, where a higher Criticality (C) value indicates a higher criticality [17]. This paper implements both FMEA and FMECA methodologies for systematic failure analysis.

B. Grey Relational Analysis (GRA)

Grey Relational Analysis (GRA) is a robust multi-criteria decision-making (MCDM) tool that effectively evaluates and compares multiple options under conditions of incomplete or uncertain information [11]. The core idea of GRA is derived from Grey Theory, introduced by Deng in 1982 to analyze similarity relationships in dynamic processes. In GRA, the optimal solution is determined by identifying the alternative series that closely resemble the reference series [18]. The GRA methodology can be described in the following steps. Suppose the initial decision matrix R is as follows:

$$R = \begin{bmatrix} x_{11} & x_{12} & \dots & x_{1n} \\ x_{21} & x_{22} & \dots & x_{2n} \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ x_{m1} & x_{m2} & \dots & x_{mn} \end{bmatrix} \quad (1 \leq i \leq m, 1 \leq j \leq n)$$

Step 1: Standardize the decision matrix R' by following these steps:

$$R' = \begin{bmatrix} x'_{11} & x'_{12} & \dots & x'_{1n} \\ x'_{21} & x'_{22} & \dots & x'_{2n} \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ x'_{m1} & x'_{m2} & \dots & x'_{mn} \end{bmatrix} \quad (1 \leq i \leq m, 1 \leq j \leq n)$$

Step 2: Determine the reference series:

$$x'_0 = (x'_0(1), x'_0(2), \dots, x'_0(n))$$

where $x'_0(j)$ is the standardized and largest value in j-th factor.

Step 3: Compute the difference $\Delta_{0i}(j)$ between the reference and alternative series:

$$\Delta_{0i}(j) = |x'_0(j) - x'_{ij}|$$

$$\Delta = \begin{bmatrix} \Delta'_{01}(1) & \Delta'_{01}(2) \dots & \Delta'_{01}(n) \\ \Delta'_{02}(1) & \Delta'_{02}(2) \dots & \Delta'_{02}(n) \\ \dots & \dots & \dots \\ \Delta'_{0m}(1) & \Delta'_{0m}(2) \dots & \Delta'_{0m}(n) \end{bmatrix} \quad (1 \leq i \leq m, 1 \leq j \leq n)$$

Step 4: Calculate the Grey Relational Coefficient (GRC):

$$r_{0i}(j) = \frac{\min_i \min_j \Delta_{0i}(j) + \delta \max_i \max_j \Delta_{0i}(j)}{\Delta_{0i}(j) + \delta \max_i \max_j \Delta_{0i}(j)}$$

where δ is an identification coefficient, typically set to 0.5 for providing a good stability, and the GRC is a similarity indicator between the reference and alternative series.

Step 5: Calculate the grey relational degree b_i :

$$b_i = \sum_{j=1}^n w_j r_{0i}(j)$$

where w_j represents the criteria weight, and $\sum_{i=1}^n w_j = 1$.

The resulting grey relational degree values can be used to rank the alternatives based on the similarity between the reference series and alternative series, with higher b_i indicating a preferable alternative.

Fig. 1: Smart Microgrid's Ecosystem

C. Deep Embedded Clustering (DEC) Algorithm

Deep Embedded Clustering (DEC) is a powerful unsupervised learning algorithm that combines Deep Learning and clustering techniques. Unlike traditional clustering algorithms, the DEC algorithm employs Neural Networks to learn low-dimensional feature representations of the data and then applies clustering methods to analyze and classify the learned features. The DEC algorithm consists of 2 stages as introduced by Xie et al [18]. In the initial pre-training stage, an Autoencoder Neural Network is employed to compress input data into a lower-dimensional space, facilitating the learning of a compact and informative representation. This stage aims to initialize the model with meaningful features that encapsulate the intrinsic structure of the data. Upon completing the pre-training, the algorithm seamlessly transitions to the clustering stage. Here, the Neural Network's encoder, now functioning as a feature extractor, transforms the data into a new representation. Introducing a clustering layer, DEC optimizes this representation to encourage features conducive to clustering. Through an iterative process of updating network parameters and refining cluster assignments, the algorithm converges to an improved state, effectively enhancing the overall clustering performance. The DEC algorithm's strength lies in its autonomous discovery of intricate data patterns,

making it particularly valuable for unsupervised learning tasks where labeled data is scarce or unavailable.

III. CASE STUDY

The objective of this research is to enhance the FMEA process by identifying potential failures throughout the system infrastructure of Smart Microgrids. For this task, we introduce Smart Microgrids, outline the formulation of problems and causes within the infrastructure, and proceed with a case study and experimental analysis. Initial risk analysis is conducted using traditional FMEA, followed by the application of GRA analysis to establish risk priorities based on these methodologies. Additionally, a Deep Embedded Clustering algorithm is incorporated into the risk assessment process to classify failure modes with distinct criticality levels, such as low, moderate, and high-ranked risks. The novel ranking algorithm aims to optimize the reliability and resilience of Smart Microgrid systems and their digital twins by prioritizing mitigation actions for each failure mode.

A. Smart Microgrids

The use case considered in this paper is a real industrial plant located in the Barcelona province of Spain. The industrial plant is owned by environmental services company CLD which offers services to the Barcelona city for street

TABLE I: Combined Table of FMEA, FMECA and GRA Assessment

ID	Systems	Failure Mode(s)	Potential Effect(s)	Scores						Ranking		
				S	O	D	RPN	Crit	GRA	RPN	Crit	GRA
FM1	PV arrays	Energy Production Efficiency Reduction	Energy shortages	8	10	3	240	80	0.51	1	1	15
FM2	Solar Inverter	Energy Conversion Inefficiency	No AC output and can impact the energy supply	5	2	2	20	10	0.57	18	18	12
FM3	SESS	Energy Storage Capacity Reduction	Power disruptions and reduced system reliability.	5	6	2	60	30	0.55	14	6	13
FM4	Bi-directional Inverter	Energy Control Loss	Battery not charging and can destabilize the system's power distribution and energy balance	8	5	3	120	40	0.61	7	3	8
FM5	EV Charging Points	Charging Station Service Disruption	Inconvenience to users	5	5	2	50	25	0.62	17	10	5
FM6	Industrial Assets	Equipment Breakdown	Disrupt production, leading to system downtime and inefficiencies.	5	4	3	60	20	0.68	13	13	2
FM7	AC Bus Bar	Electrical Distribution Disruption	Electrical disruptions can cause system-wide damage and power distribution interruptions.	8	4	2	64	32	0.61	12	5	9
FM8	IoT Gateway	Sensor Data Communication Failure	Lead to data inaccuracies and affect system performance	7	6	4	168	42	0.47	4	2	17
FM9	SCADA	Monitoring and Control Disruption	Result in data loss and interruptions in the entire system	8	4	4	128	32	0.58	6	4	10
FM10	Communication Module	Data Security Breach	Compromise data integrity and user privacy, impacting the system's security.	9	3	7	189	27	0.47	3	9	16
FM11	Data Storage Module	Data Corruption	Lead to data inaccuracies, potentially affecting system-wide operations.	9	3	8	216	27	0.46	2	8	18
FM12	Diagnosis Module	Diagnostic Algorithm Inaccuracy	Incorrect system health assessments and potential system damage	5	4	4	80	20	0.62	9	14	6
FM13	Digital Twins	Digital Twin Data Inaccuracy	Incorrect system behavior predictions and potential system damage	5	4	6	120	20	0.57	8	15	11
FM14	Control Module	Control Algorithm Inaccuracy	Device misconfigurations and system inefficiencies	7	4	6	168	28	0.52	5	7	14
FM15	Electric Vehicle Optimizer	Optimization Algorithm Inaccuracy	Suboptimal electric vehicle charging can impact efficiency and lead to potential inefficiencies.	5	4	3	60	20	0.68	15	16	1
FM16	Industry Assets Optimizer	Optimization Algorithm Inaccuracy	Suboptimal asset use can affect system efficiency and potentially lead to inefficiencies.	5	5	3	75	25	0.65	10	11	4
FM17	Techno-assessment Tool	Assessment Algorithm Inaccuracy	Incorrect evaluations and potential system inefficiencies	4	5	3	60	20	0.61	16	17	7
FM18	Graphical User Interface	User Interface Malfunction	Frustrate users	5	5	3	75	25	0.65	11	12	3

cleaning and waste collection, as well as specialized services to industry, such as waste management and recovery. To carry out its operations, the company employs a fleet of Electric Vehicles (EVs), aligning with its commitment to zero emissions by meeting the electricity demand of these EVs through photovoltaic panels installed at the industrial plant [19]. The image shown in Fig. 1 represents the entire Smart Microgrid Ecosystem of the CLD industrial plant. The Smart Microgrid Ecosystem is a comprehensive cyber-physical system composed of nine physical subsystems and nine cyber subsystems. The physical subsystems collectively form the microgrid and encompass PV arrays, solar inverters, Stationary Energy Storage Systems (SESS), bi-directional inverters, Elec-

tric Vehicle Charging Points (EVCP), Industrial Assets (IAS), IoT gateways, SCADA, and AC Bus combiner boxes. On the other hand, the cyber subsystems constitute the IoT cloud platform, consisting of a communication module, data storage and management system, EV/EVCP optimizer, IAS optimizer, techno-economic assessment tool, control module, diagnosis module, digital twins of the microgrid, and a Graphical User Interface (GUI). Moreover, the Smart Microgrid Ecosystem is also influenced by different external factors like availability of utility grid, compliance with Smart energy Grid Architecture Model (SGAM) and different standards, environmental factors, external communication networks, energy markets, etc. Fig. 1 also represents a boundary diagram of the entire Smart

Microgrid Ecosystem along with the different types of interfaces used between different subsystems for the integration in the Smart Microgrid Ecosystem. The three different interfaces used are physical connection, energy transfer and information transfer as highlighted in the Fig. 1. This integrated system seamlessly combines physical and cyber components to enhance the efficiency and functionality of the CLD smart microgrid, offering a sophisticated and interconnected solution for energy management.

B. FMEA and FMECA study

This paper focuses on the IoT cloud platform’s control module, crucial for overseeing system functionality by detecting, identifying, and resolving faults, akin to FMEA. The module facilitates user access to expert knowledge encapsulated in the FMEA document, ensuring system reliability. It also prioritizes and ranks faults in the Smart Microgrid Ecosystem, addressing challenges in real-time monitoring and analysis. The paper dedicates itself to achieving these control module objectives. There are different types of FMEA like Design FMEA, Process FMEA, System FMEA, Software FMEA, Service FMEA, Assembly FMEA, Part FMEA, etc. for different applications and purposes [14]. The complexity of the Smart Microgrid Ecosystem, comprising 18 distinct cyber-physical subsystems, makes conducting a detailed FMEA challenging at the subsystem and part levels. Consequently, this paper undertakes a system-level FMEA to provide a comprehensive overview. It is important to note that the future scope of this research extends to conducting FMEA analyses for each individual subsystem. Table I provides a comprehensive overview of the FMEA assessment conducted on the Smart Microgrid Ecosystem, as detailed in section II. The FMEA table systematically outlines all 18 cyber-physical systems within the Smart Microgrid Ecosystem, presenting a single failure mode associated with each subsystem and the potential effects resulting from such failures. In evaluating the severity, occurrence, and detectability of failure modes, scores were derived from relevant reference papers with similar systems [20]–[22]. Additionally, for aspects related to cyber elements or software modules, input and expertise were sought from professionals within the IT and software development team. Finally, the RPN for each subsystem is obtained by multiplying the values for severity (S), occurrence (O), and detectability (D). Similarly, Criticality is obtained by multiplying the values for severity (S) and occurrence (O). Table I summarises the entire FMEA and FMECA assessment with the scores and rankings of all the failure modes of the Smart Microgrid Ecosystem at system level.

C. GRA Analysis and DEC Implementation

The GRA approach is performed based on the previous FMEA analysis. To determine the GRC, the study compares four risk factors associated with the failure modes (RPN and an extra parameter called criticality) to the standard series. Based on the obtained parameters from FMEA process, we compute the difference between reference and alternate series

and then the correlation coefficient as defined in Step 3 and 4 of section II. To determine the degree of relation, it is essential to initially determine the relative weights of the risk factors. Finally, we calculate the grey relational degree by formula defined in Step 5 which allows us to determine priorities. A degree of relation closer to 1 indicates that the failure mode is nearer to the optimal value, and thus, a lower degree of relation signifies a higher risk priority.

TABLE II: Failure Modes and Clusters

Clusters	Failure Modes	Item / Function
Cluster 1	FM1	PV arrays
	FM2	Solar Inverter
	FM3	SESS
	FM8	IoT Gateway
	FM9	SCADA
	FM10	Communication Module
	FM11	Data Storage Module
	FM13	Digital Twins
Cluster 2	FM14	Control Module
	FM4	Bi-directional Inverter
	FM5	EV Charging Points
	FM7	AC Bus Bar
	FM12	Diagnosis Module
Cluster 3	FM17	Techno-assessment Tool
	FM6	Industrial Assets
	FM15	Electric Vehicle Optimizer
	FM16	Industry Assets Optimizer
	FM18	Graphical User Interface

Finally, to prioritize the identified failure modes, a Deep Learning-based classification methodology is used employed to rank them based on their criticality levels. In practice, fault modes are generally divided into three categories - low risk, moderate risk, and high risk. To achieve this, we employ a novel algorithm called Deep Embedded Clustering (DEC), which utilizes Neural Networks, specifically Autoencoders, to learn the underlying data representations and subsequently classify fault modes into distinct groups according to their criticality levels using the K-means algorithm. The results of the RPN risk factors and the GRA values are comparatively listed in Table I, revealing variations in the importance of different failure modes between the two methods. However While, the clustering results are provided in Table II, while the groups of cluster groups are depicted in Fig. 2.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

There are two main results of this work, one is the comparative study of the failure modes of the Smart Microgrid Ecosystem using the FMEA, FMECA and GRA analysis provided in Table I. However, Whereas the other result involves clustering the failure modes using the DEC method. As suggested by Xie et al, a Silhouette score of 0.75 is usually required for a cluster to be considered good, so thus we select a threshold for our learning and perform the DEC method [18]. According to the rankings in Table II, the top priority issues are included in Cluster 1 highlighting the need of timely detection and improved prevention mechanisms. Decision makers prioritize addressing these most urgent problems for improvement initiatives. Subsequently, Cluster 2 includes moderate risk

Fig. 2: Failure Modes Grouped in Different Clusters

failure modes, following the corresponding reasonable actions from the decision support system. The least critical problem is identified by Cluster 3, where problems associated with corresponding failures can be given less priority. For high- and medium- priority cluster faults, the development and implementation of fault prediction models are recommended. In contrast, low-priority cluster faults do not require the use of such prediction models.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This study enhances the reliability of the Smart Microgrid Ecosystem by applying Machine Learning techniques to traditional FMEA and FMECA risk assessment methodologies. The novel methodology integrates an enhanced FMEA method with GRA and the Deep Embedded Clustering (DEC) algorithm for data processing. After conducting expert analysis on various failure modes within Smart Microgrids and applying the DEC algorithm, the failure modes are categorized into three distinct groups. Cluster 3 indicates low-risk priority failure modes primarily due to Electric Vehicle, industry assets and graphical UI, gradually influencing the system's dynamic development. Cluster 1 exhibits high severity, impacting overall ecosystem function requiring intensified prevention and monitoring efforts, while Cluster 2 involves moderate risks associated with components like diagnosis module, EV charging points, etc. Machine learning's data-processing capability, although advantageous in this small knowledge base, promises greater efficacy with an expanded GRA analysis of Smart Microgrid Ecosystem failure modes. The proposed novel method proves effective for managing complex systems like Microgrids, suggesting improvements for future research in knowledge base expansion and enhanced classification logic for reliability analysis and Decision Support Systems (DSS).

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